

Oral health and salivary changes in chronic renal insufficiency patients: what to consider in the dental approach?

Saúde oral e alterações salivares em pacientes com insuficiência renal crônica: o que considerar na abordagem odontológica?

Salud bucal y cambios salivares en pacientes con insuficiencia renal crónica: qué considerar en el abordaje odontológico?

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ABSTRACT

The kidneys are multifunctional organs that play a fundamental role in maintaining the normal volume of body fluids, in electrolyte and acid-base balance and in the excretion of waste products and pharmacological compounds. Patients with Chronic Renal Insufficiency (CRI) have a high rate of systemic alterations and losing the kidneys' regulatory and excretory functions causes oral manifestations and numerous complications. Individuals undergoing hemodialysis often consider oral health maintenance to be a low priority. The current study aims to describe the common oral manifestations and salivary alterations in individuals with CRI undergoing hemodialysis treatment. 68 articles published in English from PubMed, Wiley Library, Science Direct and Scholar Google were examined to compose an integrative review. One of the first symptoms that occur in more than 90% of patients with kidney disease is uremic odor associated or not with uremic stomatitis, which is characterized by the presence of a red mucous membrane covered with a thin pseudomembrane. Hemodialysis patients are more susceptible to oral pathogens. It is necessary to be aware that oral surgeries on these patients, must be performed the day after hemodialysis treatment so that the drug has been metabolized and thus there are no major complications. Conservative dental care for patients with chronic renal failure seeks to restore oral health and eliminate potential sources of infection.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Failure, Renal Insufficiency, Oral Health.

RESUMO

Os rins são órgãos multifuncionais que desempenham um papel fundamental na manutenção do volume normal de fluidos corporais, no equilíbrio eletrolítico e ácido-base e na excreção de resíduos e compostos farmacológicos. Pacientes com Insuficiência Renal Crônica (IRC) apresentam uma alta taxa de alterações sistêmicas e a perda das funções reguladoras e excretoras dos rins causa manifestações orais e inúmeras complicações. Indivíduos em hemodiálise frequentemente consideram a manutenção da saúde bucal como uma baixa prioridade. O presente estudo tem como objetivo descrever as manifestações orais comuns e alterações salivares em indivíduos com IRC em tratamento hemodialítico. 68 artigos publicados em inglês do PubMed, Wiley Library, Science Direct e Scholar Google foram examinados para compor uma revisão integrativa. Um dos primeiros sintomas que ocorrem em mais de 90% dos pacientes com doença renal é o odor urêmico associado ou não à estomatite urêmica, que é caracterizada pela presença de uma mucosa vermelha coberta por uma fina pseudomembrana. Pacientes em hemodiálise são mais suscetíveis a patógenos orais. É preciso estar ciente de que as cirurgias orais nesses pacientes, devem ser realizadas no dia seguinte ao tratamento de hemodiálise para que o medicamento tenha sido metabolizado e assim não haja maiores complicações. O tratamento odontológico conservador para pacientes com insuficiência renal crônica busca restaurar a saúde bucal e eliminar potenciais fontes de infecção.

Palavras-chave: Falência Renal Crônica, Insuficiência Renal, Saúde Bucal.

RESUMEN

Los riñones son órganos multifuncionales que juegan un papel fundamental en el mantenimiento del volumen normal de líquidos corporales, en el equilibrio electrolítico y ácido-base y en la excreción de productos de desecho y compuestos farmacológicos. Los pacientes con Insuficiencia Renal Crónica (IRC) presentan una alta tasa de alteraciones sistémicas y la pérdida de las funciones reguladoras y excretoras de los riñones provoca manifestaciones orales y numerosas complicaciones. Los individuos sometidos a hemodiálisis a menudo consideran que el mantenimiento de la salud bucal es una prioridad baja. El presente estudio tiene como objetivo describir las manifestaciones orales y alteraciones salivales comunes en individuos con IRC sometidos a tratamiento de hemodiálisis. Se examinaron 68 artículos publicados en inglés de PubMed, Wiley Library, Science Direct y Scholar Google para componer una revisión integradora. Uno de los primeros síntomas que se presenta en más del 90% de los pacientes con enfermedad renal es el olor urémico asociado o no a estomatitis urémica, que se caracteriza por la presencia de una mucosa roja cubierta por una pseudomembrana delgada. Los pacientes en hemodiálisis son más susceptibles a los patógenos orales. Es necesario tener en cuenta que las cirugías bucales en estos pacientes, deben realizarse al día siguiente del tratamiento de hemodiálisis para que el fármaco haya sido metabolizado y así no haya complicaciones mayores. El cuidado odontológico conservador para pacientes con insuficiencia renal crónica busca restablecer la salud bucal y eliminar posibles focos de infección.

Palabras clave: Fallo Renal Crónico, Insuficiencia Renal, Salud Bucal.

1. INTRODUCTION

The kidneys are multifunctional organs that play a fundamental role in maintaining the normal volume of body fluids, in electrolyte and acid-base balance, and according to Dembowska *et al.*, (2023), the excretion of waste products and pharmacological compounds it's an essential function to the organism. In addition, they are part of the production and metabolism of various hormones, including renin, erythropoietin and prostaglandins, promoting the activation of vitamin D and controlling the production of red blood cells (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020; Dembowska *et al.*, 2023).

Patients with Chronic Renal Insufficiency (CRI) have a high rate of systemic alterations and also advanced damage to kidney function, considerably affecting diagnosis and therapeutic management (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020). Losing the kidneys' regulatory and excretory functions causes oral manifestations and numerous complications (Santos *et al.*, 2023).

The global incidence of kidney failure is rising and people receiving chronic dialysis are increasing (Arasu; Jegatheesan; Sivakumaran, 2022). Hemodialysis is one of the treatments for patients with chronic renal failure (Oktarina; Sulistiawan, 2020). Due to the high levels of psychological stress and lack of time to perform dental care, individuals undergoing hemodialysis often consider oral health maintenance to be a low priority and researchers report that individuals with psychological stress are more likely to exhibit risk behaviors related to oral health, which leads to a significant increase in the risk of tooth loss (Cardoso *et al.*, 2021).

At some levels, kidney function loss requires the patient to undergo hemodialysis, a procedure in which a machine cleans and filters the blood when the kidney can no longer perform this role. After

diagnosis, patients need to be classified according to the stage of the disease, which is closely related to the prognosis. In some cases, a transplant is necessary, in which case special blood tests are carried out to determine the kidney's compatibility (Cardoso *et al.*, 2021; Santos *et al.*, 2023).

The reflex of systemic pathological conditions in the oral cavity is thoroughly investigated due to the multidisciplinary approach that has recently been addressed. In addition, changes in the oral cavity have been associated with increased morbidity and mortality in patients with CRI, yet, this factor is often neglected and the understanding of this issue is important (Cardoso *et al.*, 2021; Santos *et al.*, 2023).

Advanced age and common comorbidities, such as diabetes and concomitant medications with immune dysfunction states, may also increase the risk of consequences for periodontal disease and other oral pathologies in individuals with CRI (Santos *et al.*, 2023). The current study aims to describe the most common oral manifestations and salivary alterations in individuals with CRI undergoing hemodialysis treatment.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

It is estimated that Chronic Renal insufficiency (CRI) has a worldwide prevalence of 11% to 13% among adults (Santos *et al.*, 2023). In the United States, approximately 11% of the population has CRF at some stage of evolution (Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey). In mainland China, the prevalence of CRI is reported to be 10.8%. In Brazil, the prevalence is approximately 9% (Santos *et al.*, 2023).

Currently, between 30% and 50% of cases of end-stage CRI in industrialized countries are due to diabetes and hypertension. As a result of weakened immunity, most patients with CRI carry other illnesses that contribute to the worsening of their systemic condition (Dembowska *et al.*, 2023). In Germany, approximately one in ten adults has CRI. Its most serious consequence is generally not the development of end-stage renal failure, but rather the markedly increased cardiovascular risk as kidney function declines (Hahn; Strutz, 2024).

Concerning medications for kidney transplant patients, it is necessary to use immunosuppressants, which are used by 100% of these patients, except in cases of transplantation between identical twins (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020; Santos *et al.*, 2023). In chronic kidney disease, altered mineral metabolism leads to calcium deposition throughout the vasculature and this vascular calcification contributes to the elevated risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD) and all-cause mortality in people with CRI (Shea *et al.*, 2022).

It is necessary to be aware that oral surgeries on these patients, must be performed the day after hemodialysis treatment so that the drug has been metabolized and thus there are no major complications. In addition, potassium and sodium levels must be checked, the former due to the state of hyperkalemia that, if not diagnosed preoperatively, can lead to the patient's death, with the appropriate potassium level being less than 5.5 mEq/L, as this is usually increased during and after surgery (Shea *et al.*, 2022; Dembowska *et al.*, 2023; Santos *et al.*, 2023; Hahn; Strutz, 2024).

3. METHODOLOGY

A literature review is formally defined as a systematic gathering strategy and consolidating past research (Jesus *et al.*, 2024). To sustain an integrative literature review, (N= 68) articles published in English from PubMed, Wiley Library, Science Direct and Scholar Google were examined. After the assessment, only 15 articles published between 2014-2024 (last 10 years) were comprised.

The terms searched were “chronic renal insufficiency” AND “oral health” AND “kidney failure,” AND “hemodialysis” AND “oral manifestation” AND “chronic renal failure”. To identify empirical studies that have applied network analysis to analyze the process and to acquire the standard research, measures described in **Flowchart 1** were followed, as displayed:

Flowchart 1. Description of the methodology used.

Source: elaborated by the authors (2024).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data has shown that Iron deficiency decreases the buffering capability of saliva, depriving it of its ability to neutralize pH changes and protect oral tissues against acids from food or dental plaque. Additionally, chronic kidney disease patients are often prone to periodontitis and inflammation in the oral mucosa (Dembowska *et al.*, 2023). The articles reviewed report numerous pieces of knowledge that are necessary for dental practice when involving any chronic kidney disease patient.

4.1 Chronic Renal Insufficiency

Chronic renal insufficiency (CRI) is a diagnosis that refers to the advanced and usually irreversible loss of the kidney, compromising the glomerular filtration. It is characterized by the decay of the biochemical and physiological functions of all the body's systems, secondary to the accumulation of catabolites (uremic toxins), alterations in the hydro electrolytic and acid-base balance, metabolic acidosis, hypovolemia, hyperkalemia, hyperphosphatemia, anemia and hormonal disorders, hyperparathyroidism, infertility, growth retardation, among others (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020).

Initially, CRI can be treated using conventional therapies, such as dietary treatment, medication, and blood pressure control (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020). A dialysis program is indicated when conservative treatment is unable to maintain the patient's quality of life and when significant signs and symptoms of uremia appear. The diagnosis of Renal Insufficiency in the initial phase can be indicated by a combination of non-specific manifestations, such as fatigue, and weight loss which can even lead to anorexia, pruritus, nausea or hemolysis, and hypertension, among others.

Systemic diseases such as diabetes mellitus, chronic glomerulonephritis, hypertension, obstruction of the urinary system, hereditary lesions (polycystic kidney disease), disorders, and toxic, environmental and occupational agents (lead, mercury, chromium and cadmium) are also aspects that can lead to renal insufficiency (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020). Thus, the causes of CRF range from primary kidney diseases to systemic diseases affecting the kidneys and diseases of the urinary tract.

Kidney transplantation is the treatment that best improves the quality of life of these patients and also improves their survival rate, which can reach 80% within a year of transplantation (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020).

4.2 Oral Manifestations

This systemic condition can lead to additional systemic alterations, and in dentistry, it is important to understand that patients affected by this disorder have a significant number of oral manifestations. One of the first symptoms that occur in more than 90% of patients with kidney disease is uremic odor associated or not with uremic stomatitis, which is characterized by the presence of a red mucous membrane covered with a thin pseudomembrane (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020).

Dembowska *et al.*, (2023) affirm that oral mucosal abnormalities may take nonspecific and disease-specific forms nonspecific symptoms of chronic kidney disease, white and red oral mucosa lesions in leukoplakia and erythroplakia have been described. Lichenoid lesions have also been reported due to disease and pharmacotherapy (Dembowska *et al.*, 2023).

The oral alterations associated with chronic renal failure are secondary to the systemic manifestations and are identified according to the severity of the condition, as well as being related to drug therapy, renal osteodystrophy, immunosuppression, restricted fluid intake and bone loss. Patients with this systemic disease have numerous oral manifestations, such as pallor of the oral mucosa, xerostomia, dental calculus, enamel hypoplasia, uremic breath, periodontal disease, mucosal lesions, malignant lesions and fungal infections, and less frequently, gingival hyperplasia (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020; Dembowska *et al.*, 2023).

A specific mucosal manifestation of renal dysfunction may be the so-called uremic stomatitis reported in this group of patients. Cases of uremic stomatitis mimicking the appearance of hairy leukoplakia on the dorsal and lateral surfaces of the tongue have been reported in the literature (Dembowska *et al.*, 2023).

Figures 1. Oral Condition in Chronic Renal Insufficiency Patients. (A – White Lesion; B – Recurrent Herpes Labiali; C – Hyperkeratos; D – Hairy Tongue).

Source: Dembowska *et al.*, (2023)

Dembowska *et al.*, (2023) discuss that oral diseases affect more than 2% of the population and the oral mucosa of patients with renal disease becomes susceptible to the occurrence of pathologic lesions and metabolic abnormalities due to water-electrolyte anomalies, in addition to continuous irritation by toxic metabolites associated with the general disease that are present in their saliva, as well as a predisposition to xerostomia (**Chart 1**).

Chart 1. Dental abnormalities resulting from chronic kidney disease applied in chart format, according to Dembowska et al., (2023)

Prevalence and Nature of Disorder

Source: elaborated by the authors (2024)

The occurrence of taste disorders is also influenced by high urea concentration, which is observed in patients with CRI. Another unpleasant symptom is halitosis, i.e., bad breath. Hemodialysis patients are more susceptible to oral pathogens. Numerous pathogens are present in these patients, including *Prevotella intermedia*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, and *Candida albicans* (Dembowska *et al.*, 2023; Santos *et al.*, 2023).

In peritoneal dialysis patients, periodontitis is much more common than in healthy patients and is also associated with poorer patient nutrition (malnutrition) and higher inflammatory markers in the blood (Dembowska *et al.*, 2023). Long-term immune suppression increases the risk of developing oral candidiasis and oral cancers (Velan; Sheller, 2021).

Reduced erythropoietin and the resultant anemia lead to pallor of the oral mucosa. Platelet aggregation is altered during uremia. This situation, combined with the use of heparin and other anticoagulants in hemodialysis, leads patients to become predisposed to ecchymosis, petechiae, and hemorrhages in the oral cavity.

Stomatitis, mucositis, and glossitis can cause pain and inflammation of the tongue and oral mucosa. Altered taste sensations, dysgeusia, as well as bacterial and candidiasis infections, can develop due to the

underlying renal disease. Candidiasis is seen as patients lose the ability to fight infections and is more frequent in transplant and hemodialysis patients because of generalized immunosuppression.

Patients with chronic kidney disease have been noted to have a high burden of periodontitis, and several shared risk factors have been associated with the prevalence and severity of both conditions. Otherwise, the precise relationship between the two conditions, and the extent to which each may contribute to the development of the other, remains a matter of debate (Parsegian *et al.*, 2022).

4.3 Salivary Changes

According to Santos *et al.*, (2023), the typical pH of saliva is 6 to 7, which means it is slightly acidic. Normal flow for unstimulated saliva is slightly greater than 0.1 mL/min and salivary pH can range from 5.3 to 7.8. Saliva is a valuable oral fluid and is essential for the preservation and maintenance of oral health. However, it receives little attention until the quantity or quality declines. In addition, saliva acts as an antibody to bacterial antigens and works to aggregate or group bacteria, thus inhibiting bacterial binding to host tissues (Gowher, 2023; Santos *et al.*, 2023).

Salivary glands secrete fluid containing immunological and non-immunological agents to protect teeth and mucosal surfaces. The immunological content of saliva includes IgA, IgG and IgM. The non-immune salivary contents are proteins, mucins, peptides and enzymes (Santos *et al.*, 2023). Dentists must know if patients with CRI undergoing hemodialysis treatment present salivary alterations and oral disorders on a more extensive scale than with healthy individuals (Gowher, 2023; Santos *et al.*, 2023).

Xerostomia is one of the concerns most commonly presented in all patients with CRI because it is a result of hyposalivation, consumption of medications and also low fluid intake - the latter is part of the medical recommendations for individuals with CRI to maintain a water balance in the organism (Gowher, 2023) (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Xerostomia development in Renal Disease Patients.

Source: elaborated by the authors (2024)

Mucosal pallor, on the other hand, is portrayed in the literature as a consequence of the anemic condition and the low production of erythropoietin (a glycoprotein that controls the production of red blood cells) in individuals with CRI. Gingival bleeding in these individuals is related to the increased occurrence of gingivitis and periodontitis and this bleeding, in addition to being a consequence of inefficient oral hygiene, is also associated in the literature with a dysregulation of the serum calcium-phosphate product, factors that contribute to the formation of dental calculus (Velan; Sheller, 2021; Gowher, 2023).

The uremic breath present in most patients is justified in the literature as a consequence of the high presence of urea in saliva and the uremic fetor occurs as a result of a high salivary concentration of urea, which is converted to ammonia (Gowher, 2023). Xerostomia and hyposalivation are highly prevalent in end-stage renal disease patients according to the research developed by Laheij *et al.*, (2021).

Furthermore, individuals with chronic renal failure undergoing hemodialysis treatment are more prone to changes in both the quantity and quality of saliva, as well as having a greater number of lesions/oral alterations (Velan; Sheller, 2021).

4.4 Dental Care

With greater knowledge about this population and their needs, it will be easier to prevent and treat possible oral cavity injuries and improve these individuals’ general health, preventing them from being affected by opportunistic infections related to the immune system (Santos *et al.*, 2023).

Guidelines for dental management of adult solid organ transplant patients recommend that all patients identified as needing transplant be comprehensively assessed. A clinical and radiographic dental examination may reveal acute and/or chronic dental conditions that will pose a risk to the post-transplant immune-compromised patient (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021; Velan; Sheller, 2021; Gowher, 2023).

It is recommended that dentists provide only emergency care for dental infections during the period of maximum immune suppression immediately post-transplant. Accordingly, dental treatments such as complete removal of calculus, restorations, endodontic interventions, or extractions required to treat active dental disease(s) and remove all potential origins of acute or chronic oral infection should be achieved before kidney transplantation (Guevara *et al.*, 2014; Velan; Sheller, 2021).

Depending upon the patient's age, oral hygiene coaching should involve the patient and/or their parent, stressing the relationship between hygiene habits and oral health (Gowher, 2023). Daily use of an antimicrobial mouth rinse may be conducted for selected patients (Velan; Sheller, 2021; Gowher, 2023).

Once a patient has progressed to the post-transplant maintenance phase, regular dental care may resume. This may include preventive services and elective treatments (e.g., esthetic restorations, orthodontics) to normalize appearance, enhance self-esteem, and improve oral health and well-being (Guevara *et al.*, 2014; Velan; Sheller, 2021; Gowher, 2023).

The dentist should be aware of the burden of care faced by transplant patients and should have a role in supporting adherence to medications and other parts of the post-transplant care plan (Velan; Sheller, 2021). Observance with dental recommendations following kidney transplant has been positively associated with family education level and supportive parents were considered critical to success (Guevara *et al.*, 2014).

Guevara *et al.*, (2014) demonstrate that the change in fluid volume and hemodialysis itself impacts cardiac behavior, creating a stress mechanism that may play a role in the development of endocarditis. Thus, when dental treatment is invasive, although it does not indicate antibiotic prophylaxis according to the American Heart Association, its use should be reconsidered on a case-by-case basis.

Before executing dental procedures on hemodialysis patients, the dentist must consider some important points. First, the issue is that patients generally use an arteriovenous fistula that allows easy access for the administration of heparin, which promotes an anticoagulant effect, allowing the blood to pass through the dialysis equipment without clotting (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021).

Therefore, it is necessary to be aware that oral surgeries on these patients, must be performed the day after hemodialysis treatment so that the drug has been metabolized and thus there are no major complications (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021). In addition, potassium and sodium levels must be checked, the former due to the state of hyperkalemia that, if not diagnosed preoperatively, can lead to the patient's death, with the appropriate potassium level being less than 5.5 mEq/L, as this is usually increased during and after surgery (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021).

In addition, patients are often treated with antihypertensive drugs. It is important to control stress during dental care, which could increase systolic pressure, by using a pressure monitor before and during dental care. The use of sedation should be considered to avoid variations in blood pressure caused by stress. As dialysis patients are exposed to a large number of transfusions and are immunosuppressed, there is an increased risk of infection, such as hepatitis B and C, tuberculosis and HIV. It is therefore essential for these patients to have regular check-ups and for the dental surgeon to take care of biosafety (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021; Velan; Sheller, 2021).

4.5 Pharmacological Therapy Considerations

It's important to analyze renal function, the dose of the drug, and circulating levels of the drug and evaluate the drugs' pharmacokinetic interactions, metabolic overloads, interference in laboratory tests, and elimination capacity by dialysis. Analgesics, such as paracetamol, can be used safely in low and moderate doses, but caution should be exercised when using higher doses (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020).

Aspirin and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) should be avoided due to their antiplatelet action, which increases the risk of bleeding. They are also nephrotoxic and cause a decrease in kidney function. Centrally-acting analgesics that are metabolized in the liver can be used safely (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020; Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021).

Medications such as codeine, morphine, fentanyl, naloxone and pentazocine are metabolized in the liver, so changes in dose are usually not necessary. When prescribing antibiotic therapy, the post-antibiotic effect should be checked, which represents the time during which the growth of bacteria is prevented (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020; Velan; Sheller, 2021; Santos *et al.*, 2023).

The use of tetracycline, aminoglycosides and erythromycin derivatives is highly practical, despite they are nephrotoxic and contribute to an increase in blood urea nitrogen levels, making them contraindicated in the presence of kidney disease. They are metabolized by dialysis, so it is recommended to administer the usual dose at the end of dialysis to maintain adequate therapeutic levels in the interdialytic period (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020; Velan; Sheller, 2021; Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021).

Amoxicillin, clindamycin, erythromycin and metronidazole can be used at the usual dose and are the first choice, although they can alter the metabolism of immunosuppressive drugs. When these drugs are used, the dosage interval should be extended, stressing that the dose should be administered after dialysis since most of them are metabolized with dialysis. For this explanation, precise protocols have been established by the diverse medical and dental associations (Magalhães; Carvalho; Pinto, 2020).

The antibiotics of choice will be those that act on the oral microbial flora, such as penicillin or amoxicillin; or clindamycin or azithromycin in patients allergic to penicillin (Guevara *et al.*, 2014). When the use of antibiotic, analgesic and anti-inflammatory medication is necessary, drugs with hepatic metabolism should be used (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021).

Conclusively, patients with kidney disease should be treated with attention, as the existence of a focus of infection in the oral cavity can lead to complications which, if not treated, increase the morbidity of these patients, with the risk of bacteremia and rejection of the transplanted kidney (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021; Guevara *et al.*, 2014; Velan; Sheller, 2021).

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Conservative dental care for patients with chronic renal failure seeks to restore oral health and eliminate potential sources of infection, familiarizing the patient with the importance of oral hygiene techniques and prevention. The importance of dental treatment in patients with chronic kidney disease lies in assessing the oral cavity as a possible source of infection. It is important to be aware of the risk of bleeding, infection and drug use before treating these patients. This systemic disease can have consequences that affect the oral cavity in many ways, leading to a loss of function, aesthetics and comfort.

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